

cyanide and other membranes with drops of dilute alcohol and other acids added to them. The results would show definitely whether we are getting coagulation or not in these cases.

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A Note on an Improved Device for Working a Thermostat at Low Temperatures.

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The general practice in physical chemistry is to take standard measurements at 18°C or 25°C. At Bombay the temperature of the atmosphere rarely falls below 25°C and the necessity is felt of fitting up a thermostat which would work conveniently and smoothly at 25°C.

Foote (*Z. physical. Chem.*, 1906, 33, 740) has described a thermo-regulator suitable for running a thermostat at low temperatures. The thermo-regulator is filled with toluene and mercury as the ordinary gas thermo-regulator. The head of the regulator *D* contains an inlet tube *F* and two exit tubes *E* and *G*. The method of its working, as suggested by Foote, is to admit ice-cold water continuously into the regulator by the tube *F*. When the temperature of the thermostat rises above the one required, ice-cold water entering the regulator by the tube *F* falls out from the tube *G* into the thermostat and thus lowers the temperature of the thermostat. But

when the thermostat maintains the required temperature or any temperature lower than that, water entering the thermo-regulator by the tube *F* flows out from the tube *E* to the sink. In this way a large amount of ice is consumed and is simply wasted when the thermostat runs satisfactorily.

Hickman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 3416) has also described a modified form of an arrangement for running a thermostat at low temperatures. The thermo-regulator used by him is almost of the same type as Foote's regulator but instead of passing ice-cold water continuously through the regulator he allows water at ordinary temperature to flow through it. When the temperature of the thermostat rises, this water flows out from an exit into a water-bath packed with ice, where it gets cooled, and then falls into a spiral placed in the thermostat. The spiral gets cooled and consequently the temperature of the thermostat is lowered. This method does not, as the previous one, involve the running of the ice-cold water to waste but the position of the spiral in the thermostat is not desirable because it interferes with the stirring and does not leave sufficient accommodation for other apparatus to be placed in the thermostat.

The device, which is described in the following note, avoids the waste of ice-cold water and also requires a much simpler fitting. Hickman's auxiliary water-bath has been totally dispensed with and the spiral is kept outside the thermostat and thus more space inside the thermostat is rendered available.

The thermo-regulator *D* is of the same pattern as the one used by Foote (*loc. cit.*). Water at ordinary temperature enters the thermo-regulator continuously by the tube *F* and when the temperature of the thermostat is at or below 25°C it flows out by the tube *E* to the sink. When the thermostat rises in temperature, water instead

of directly flowing out from the tube G into the thermostat (as in Foote's method) falls into the funnel H , whence it is conveyed first to a spiral K immersed in crushed ice. Water when passing through the spiral gets cooled and flows out by the other end of the spiral into the thermostat and thus adjusts the temperature.

To work this arrangement satisfactorily, it is very important that the two water exits E and G from the thermo-regulator should not have rubber tubing attached to them to carry away water but should empty directly into open funnels. In this way all syphoning action is avoided and the thermo-regulator is made more uniform in its action because there is no risk of any drop of mercury being syphoned away with water and hence no disturbance in the adjusted column of mercury takes place. This arrangement requires, of course, that the top of the spiral K should be a shade lower than the water level attainable in the funnel H . The exit end of the spiral K is covered with a piece of thick-walled rubber tubing to act as lagging. The glass vessel L which holds the crushed ice is packed with wool in the wooden box M and the thermostat A is also wrapped around with cotton wool (not shown in the figure). B is a platform made of brass-wire netting which can be raised or lowered by brass chains. The stirrer C is made of glass tubing (the brass tubing would be more robust, of course) which is fastened to the hub of a bicycle wheel through a short sleeve made of brass tubing into which it is fastened with sealing-wax. The hub of a bicycle wheel is excellent for this purpose because its spindle rotates on ball bearing and hence avoids all contact friction. The cork through which the ends of the spiral K pass has also a third outlet (not shown in the figure) which can be opened when water from the vessel L has to be run out. S is a screw to adjust the exact quantity of mercury

required in the thermo-regulator for any particular temperature.

With the modifications described above, it was found that in Bombay when the air temperature was about 30°C the thermostat holding about 40—50 gallons of water could be kept running steadily at temperature $25^{\circ} \pm 0.03$ throughout the day with a consumption of not more than 10-15 lbs. of ice and without requiring any attention whatever.

If the air temperature happens to fall below 25°C a very small flame kept below the thermostat adjusts the temperature without requiring any other alteration in the arrangement.

When the thermostat is to be used to maintain a constant temperature which is much below the room temperature, radiation from the sides of the thermostat will be great and the working of the thermostat will not be as satisfactory as at 25°C or as at any temperature which is lower but near the room temperature. It will, however, be possible to use the thermostat to maintain constant temperatures even when the temperatures are not very near the room temperature by reducing the radiation from the sides to a minimum and maintaining an adequate supply of ice-cold water. The top of the thermostat in such instances will, of course, have to be covered with a lid of some non-conducting material.

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